

NORMAL AND PATHOLOGICAL PHYSIOLOGY

ПАТОГЕНЕТИЧНИЙ ЗВ'ЯЗОК ТОКСИГЕННИХ ШТАМІВ ХЕЛІКОБАКТЕРНОЇ ІНФЕКЦІЇ НА РОЗВИТОК ЦУКРОВОГО ДІАБЕТУ ТИПУ 2. (ОГЛЯД ЛІТЕРАТУРИ)

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PATHOGENETIC RELATIONSHIP OF TOXIGENIC STRAINS OF HELICOBACTERI INFECTION TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF TYPE 2 DIABETES (LITERATURE REVIEW)

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Анотація

Продукція токсинів VacA (50-65%) та CagA є механізмом патогенної дії *H.pylori* (HP.). Відомо, саме токсигенні штами впливають на порушення роботи підшлункової залози, порушення серцево-судинної системи. Подальший такий розвиток призводить до розвитку цукрового діабету типу 2 з ускладненнями як артеріальна гіпертензія, мікроангіопатія, макроангіопатія, ураження нирок (пієлонефрит), шлункові кровотечі, тощо. Досліджено і патогенетичний зв'язок *H. pylori* із макроангіопатією, нейропатією та мікроальбумінурією, який пояснюється імуноопосередкованим ураженням ендотелію, вираженою системною запальною відповіддю, що є початковим етапом розвитку ЦД.

З огляду на високу поширеність захворювання, ускладнений перебіг та можливість виникнення рецидивів пептична виразка дванадцятипалої кишки у поєднанні із цукровим діабетом типу 2 є важливою медико-соціальною проблемою. Досягнення медицини за останні десятиліття дають можливість впровадження в практику нових класів лікарських засобів, що змінили стратегію лікування пептичної виразки дванадцятипалої кишки з урахуванням наявності супутньої патології та токсигенності штамів *H. pylori* і сприяють покращенню якості життя хворого.

Abstract

The production of VacA (50-65%) and CagA toxins is the mechanism of pathogenic action of *H.pylori* (HP.). It is known that toxigenic strains affect pancreatic dysfunction and cardiovascular system disorders. Further such development leads to the development of type 2 diabetes with complications such as hypertension, microangiopathy, macroangiopathy, kidney damage (pyelonephritis), gastric bleeding, etc. The pathogenetic connection of *H. pylori* with macroangiopathy, neuropathy and microalbuminuria, which is explained by immune-mediated damage to the endothelium, expressed by a systemic inflammatory response, which is the initial stage of the development of diabetes, was also investigated.

Due to the high prevalence of the disease, the complicated course and the possibility of relapses, peptic ulcer of the duodenum in combination with type 2 diabetes is an important medical and social problem. Advances in medicine over the last decades make it possible to introduce new classes of drugs into practice, which have changed the strategy of treating peptic ulcer of the duodenum, taking into account the presence of concomitant pathology and the toxigenicity of *H. pylori* strains and contribute to improving the patient's quality of life.

Ключові слова: Цукровий діабет, пептична виразка дванадцятипалої кишки, патогенез.

Keywords: Diabetes, peptic ulcer of the duodenum, pathogenesis.

Introduction. The production of VacA (50-65%) and CagA toxins is the mechanism of pathogenic action of *H. pylori* (HP.). One of the pathogenetic links is the effect of VacA, which can bind to receptors (RPTP α , RPTP β) in epithelial cells [1,2], thus ensuring the interaction of the strain with human kidney tumor cells and adenocarcinoma cells. [3,5]. This makes it possible to interact with gastric carcinoma cells [4,6]. By increasing the sensitivity of RPTP β receptors in some cell lines, which increases the toxicity of VacA [7]. Absence of the RPTP β receptor increases resistance to mucosal ulceration (MU) caused by the action of the toxigenic VacA strain [5,8]. The interaction of VacA with the receptors of the functional lymphocyte antigen of the first type increases the expression of leukocytes [24]. The presence of many receptors for the vacA gene can determine the diversity of its effect on CO [5, 21]. The toxin VacA, which is a "conductor" for the cytotoxin-associated protein CagA, has two informational regions (signal - (s, signal, allelic variants - s1 and s2), middle (m, middle, m1 or m2)), the combination of which leads to the formation of membrane pores with the release of chlorine ions, inhibition of T-lymphocyte activity and the occurrence of vacuolar degeneration of epithelial cells, which is the cause apoptosis [7,8,9].

According to the research of N. Guicelik et al. *H. pylori* infection was established in 75.6% of patients with T2DM [11], the increased frequency of which is explained by the development of microangiopathy of SOS, which creates favorable conditions for the survival of the microorganism [10,12]. However, N.B. Gubergritz established that the frequency of *H. pylori* infection in combination with pancreatitis (86.5%) and without it (76.7%) did not differ [22]. Vacuolizing cytotoxin, which is capable of causing pancreatotoxic effects, inhibits the exocrine function of the pancreas, and *H. pylori* infection, which reduces the synthesis and release of somatostatin (which normally inhibits gastrin production and pancreatic secretion) from D-cells of the stomach, leads to an increase in the synthesis and release of gastrin [13,15,16]. This is accompanied by a decrease in the antral density of D cells, which returns to normal after eradication [14]. The pathogenetic connection of *H. pylori* with macroangiopathy, neuropathy, and microalbuminuria was also investigated, which is explained by immune-mediated damage to the endothelium, a pronounced systemic inflammatory response, which is the initial stage of the development of diabetes [10, 12, 17].

The purpose of the study. To assess the pathogenetic relationship between the impact of toxigenic strains of *Helicobacter* infection and the development of type 2 diabetes.

Research materials and methods. Study of the literature and generalization of the purpose of the research. Review of articles with diseases that are infected with *Helicobacter* infection, diseases of the pancreas, diseases of cardiovascular pathology.

Research results. A certain group of pathogens associated with the rapid progression of insulin resistance (IR) and hyperinsulinemia (GI) has been identified. They include members of the Herpetoviridae family (in particular CMV, HSV-1, EBV), Chlamydia Pneumoniae, *Helicobacter pylori* (N. *pylori*),

Porphyromonas gingivalis [4,6,7,24,30]. Endothelial damage is known to occur as a result of direct exposure to *H. pylori* endotoxins and stimulation of systemic and local inflammation [17, 18], the ways of implementing the effects of *H. pylori* infection on the cardiovascular and endocrine systems have not been finally clarified [3, 19].

In recent years, it has been proven that there are 2 types of CagA, which differ in the sequence of amino acids: ABC type (Western) and ABD type (East Asian). AVD-type CagA binds to the SHP-2 site, acts more deeply on the epithelium and leads to severe inflammation and atrophy of the OSH [3, 11]. In Japan, ABD type CagA is found in almost all gastric cancer patients [13, 20], and in Western Europe ABC type CagA dominates, which is the cause of the development of PVDPK (90%) [11, 21].

The ability to directly damage the epithelium of the gastric mucosa is one of the characteristics of *H. pylori*, which have CagA - and VacA - phenotypes and, as a result, show the greatest cytolytic activity. The presence of the *Helicobacter pylori* *agA* gene leads to systemic inflammation due to the activation of lipid peroxidation processes and the development of metabolic intoxication [6,7,10,19,22] with a violation of the hemostasis system [28, 30], subsequently leading to the development of atherosclerosis (AS) and hypertension [23, 24], and, not excluded, and T2DM [22].

The role of NO in the development of endothelial dysfunction, which is one of the key links in the pathogenesis of T2DM, is currently proven and unquestionable [25,26,29].

NO plays an integral role as a bioregulator in the gastrointestinal tract (GI), which regulates gastric secretion and motility and plays a role in protecting the gastric mucosa from aggression factors [5, 27]. NO is one of the sources of gastrointestinal tract, namely in epithelial cells, vascular endothelium, smooth muscles, etc. During the inflammatory process of OSH and DPK, gastric secretion increases, gastric motility increases, hyperemia is observed, which indicates the presence of NO in glandular cells and vessels. A decrease in the activity of NO in all structural elements of the stomach in the case of healing of an ulcer defect indicates its role in the processes of ulcerogenesis [8, 9, 28].

In turn, ET-1 is a powerful vasoconstrictor peptide that regulates angiogenesis of vessels and, being formed under the influence of many factors (adrenaline, vasopressin), is secreted inside the vascular wall, where specific receptors are located [4,9]. It, as well as NO, plays the role of a bioregulator of the digestive system, the concentration of which in the blood plasma increases when a vessel is damaged, which is associated with an increase in its release [3, 14, 22, 23].

The combination of genotypes s1m1, s1m2, s2m1 and s2m2 determines the level of pathogenicity [5,7,25]. The s1m2 sequence encodes a signaling protein (p33), improving penetration into the epitheliocyte membrane. The middle section of DNA is responsible for the synthesis of the p58 receptor domain, and cells with the m1 genotype are able to interact with a wider range of epitheliocytes than those with the m2 genotype. This explains the high vacuolating activity of s1/m1 genotypes, moderate degree of vacuolation in the

s1/m2 genotype and its absence in the s2/m2 genotype [5, 18, 28]. The intermediate i region, which is between the s and m regions, is a marker of disease severity [22, 27], and the s1m1 genotype is considered the 32 most associated with high cytotoxicity and disease severity [16]. Strains containing a combination of s1, i1, m1 alleles are associated with the most severe diseases [15]. This relationship can be realized due to the increased ability to form anion channels, vacuolating activity and wide cellular tropism of s1/i1/m1 genotypes [17, 26]. Since vacA s1/m1 is closely associated with the cagA-positive genotype, this factor cannot be considered separately as a marker of disease severity [15]. In turn, the pathogenicity island of Cag (Cag RAI) HP, which encodes up to 27 genes, having effector proteins, penetrate through the formed pores into the epithelial cells of the host [6, 24], interacting directly with the regulators of cell polarity. It is they who affect the process of mitosis, leading to disruption of the phases of the mitotic cycle (G1 and G2) and the appearance of polyploid cells [7,9]. As a result of the above, the intracellular signaling system SHP-2 is stimulated with the production of pro-inflammatory chemokines IL-8, IL-6, activating the processes of migration of neutrophils into the CSF, contributing to the activation, etc.

The ability to directly damage the epithelium of the gastric mucosa is one of the characteristics of *H. pylori*, which have CagA - and VacA - phenotypes and, as a result, show the greatest cytolytic activity. And in the presence of the gene CarA, *Helicobacter pylori* also affects the processes of systemic inflammation due to the activation of lipid peroxide oxidation processes and due to the development of metabolic intoxication [6, 7, 10, 19, 22], disruption of the hemostasis system [3, 28], leading to the development of atherosclerosis in the future (AS) and hypertension [29], and, not excluded, and T2DM [20]. The obtained data on the influence of *H. pylori* infection on the course of the atherosclerotic process are focused on several aspects: epidemiological association, pathophysiological mechanisms, and the results of eradication therapy [6,7]. The connection between HR seropositivity and the course of the atherosclerotic process has been proven in the presence of sagA [11, 26, 28]. One of the most immunogenic antigens of HR is its HSP, which belongs to the family of bacterial Gro-EL proteins and has wide cross-reactivity both with other bacterial Gro-EL (in particular, mycobacterial) and with human HSP65 [5, 9, 15, 17]. This fact is of considerable importance, since the possibility of AS induction by HSP65 immunization [17, 27] and the level of antibodies to HSP65, which correlates with the degree of risk of vascular events [28] and can react with antigens of the atherosclerotic vascular wall [15], have been proven.], which is also an intermediate link between *H. pylori* infection and the subsequent development of cardiovascular pathology [18]. Another direction of research within the scope of the search for possible mechanisms of *H. pylori* infection interference in the course of the atherosclerotic process is to identify the effect of *Helicobacter* infection on the exchange of biologically active substances, in particular, on the synthesis of nitrogen monoxide (NO) in the endothelium, which is a regulator of hemostasis and vascular tone [11, 18, 27]. The relationship between HP infection and

pancreatic diseases remains unclear. The effect of this microorganism on the development of pancreatitis and diabetes mellitus 2 has been revealed, but studies on the spread of *Helicobacter* infection in patients with diabetes mellitus are ambiguous.

Conclusion. Due to the high prevalence of the disease, the complicated course and the possibility of relapses, peptic ulcer of the duodenum in combination with type 2 diabetes is an important medical and social problem. Advances in medicine over the last decades make it possible to introduce new classes of drugs into practice, which have changed the strategy of treating peptic ulcer of the duodenum, taking into account the presence of concomitant pathology and the toxigenicity of *H. pylori* strains and contribute to improving the patient's quality of life.

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